

OPTIMIZATION OF THE WATER DISPOSAL SYSTEM AT THE ANGRES MINING FACILITY

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Abstract: The digging works beneficial minerals solving water to the earth's surface in stage or un-stage technological diagram. According to the main technologic diagram definite numbers, the structure of digging the water, the types of establishment to it electromechanical equipment, establish water pipe. Organizing this technological diagram certainly ways the enterprises of quarry appropriate ones from main by one by processes to be done comfortable and economically effectively digging water. In this article ways of modernization present digging the water, that's the way in Angren coal quarry.

Keywords: pump, pipeline, water collector, pipeline diameter, hydraulic loss.

INTRODUCTION. To effectively conduct the mineral extraction process, the timely and complete removal of water accumulating in the deposits must be organized. This can be achieved through a strapless or step-by-step method, using pumps either separately or together (in parallel or sequentially) [1] with the water device. When organizing the process of water extraction, a technological scheme is initially drawn up based on hydro-geological, mining technological, and technical indicators of modern technology and techniques [6]. The technological scheme is necessary to determine the quality indicators of the water discharge work, including the location where the water discharge device will be installed, the type and number of pumps, the pipe layout in the mining plan, their length, and the method of discharge (step-less or step-by-step). The selection of a technological scheme in compliance with safety rules is one of the factors that ensures reliable and economically effective water extraction work [2].

MATERIAL AND METHODS. As of August 1, 2022, the data on the locations of water collection, their elevation from sea level, and the normal and maximum values of water flow at the Angren coal mine of Uzbekkomir JSC are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

№	Water catchment areas	Height from sea level (m)	Water Flow (m ³ /hour)		Water discharge device				
			Q _n	Q _m	Location	Built-in pump			
						Type	Number	Capacity, (kW)	Number
1	PK-13	799	263	850	PK-13	D-1250/125	2	630	1
						SNS-850/240		800	2
2	District "Northern"	916	68	110	District "Northern"	D-320/50	1	75	3
3	PK-22	920	393	1120	PK-22	D-1250/125	1	630	4
4	District overpass Site.№16	916	67	203	District overpass Site.№16	D-320/50	1	75	8
5	PK-12	908	45	84	PK-12	D-320/50	1	75	9
6	PK-23	905	972	1232	PK-23	D-1250/125	3	630	5,6,7
								630	
								800	

The data on the locations of water collection flow at the Angren coal mine

As of August 1, 2022, the pumping out of the water from the Angren coal mine to the Earth's surface is organized using a visual technological scheme (figure 1) that involves the phased and parallel connection of specific pumps.

Figure 1. As of August 1, 2022, the technological scheme for pumping out water from the Angren coal mine to the ground level.

According to the mine water disposal scheme, as of August 1, 2022, water collected in the PK-13 water collector at an elevation of 799 m above sea level is transferred to the PK-23 water collector at 905 m using 2 pumps (1250/125 and SNS-850/240). The water collected in the “ District Northern” water collector at a height of 916 m is pumped by the D-320/50 pump to the PK-22 water collector at a height of 920 m and then transferred to the PK-23 main water collector at a height of 905 m using a D-1250/125 pump (with an A-4Y-400 electric motor). Additionally, the water collected in the PK-12 water collector is transferred to the “ District overpass” water collector through the D-320/50 pump. The total water collected in the “ District overpass” water collector is then pumped to the main water collector PK-23 through the D-320/50 pump. Finally, the water collected in the PK-23 water collector is transferred to the main pipe using 3 D-1250/125 pumps.

A total of 9 pumps were installed at the disposal of the mining waters in the Angren coalfield to the ground level. Their total productivity is equal to [3]:

$$\sum Q = Q_1 + Q_2 + Q_3 + \dots = 5 \cdot 1250 + 3 \cdot 320 + 850 = 8060 \text{ (m}^3\text{/hour)}$$

Total power of electric drives:

$$\sum N = N_1 + N_2 + N_3 + \dots = 4 \cdot 630 + 3 \cdot 75 + 2 \cdot 800 = 4345 \text{ kWt.}$$

The following scheme is recommended for organizing the disposal of mining water from the mine to the Earth's surface[7].

Figure 2. A scheme for the placement of water collectors at the Angren mine (proposed scheme).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In the table, the water collectors “ District Northern” and PK-22 are located at an altitude of 11 m and 15 m, respectively, from the PK-23 Water Collector. If we send the water from the “ District Northern” and PK-22 water collectors to the PK-23 water collector using a water pipe or ditch[4], it will not be necessary to use pumps in the “ District Northern” and PK-22 water collectors. Not using pumps will allow us to use the pump units as backup pumps, significantly reducing electrical energy consumption. As a result, the proposed scheme will have the following benefits (see Figure 2).

According to this scheme, pumping units №3 and №4 in the “ District Northern” and PK-22 water collectors were removed and connected to the PK-23 water collector through the water pipes of the mine. Similarly, in the “ District overpass” water collector, pump №8 can be used with the help of its own flow of water to pump water into the PK-23 water collector. This reduces pressure inside the pipe and allows it to work for a longer time without becoming rapidly unsuitable [5].

Currently, a total of 9 pumping units have been installed to discharge mining water from the Angren mine to the Earth's surface. These pumps are capable of pumping out 2120 m³ of mine water per hour to the ground level.

Total power in this:

$$\sum N = N_1 + N_2 + N_3 + \dots = 4 \cdot 630 + 3 \cdot 75 + 2 \cdot 800 = 4345 \text{ kVt}$$

Overall productivity:

$$\sum Q = Q_1 + Q_2 + Q_3 + \dots = 5 \cdot 1250 + 3 \cdot 320 + 850 = 8060 \text{ (m}^3\text{/hour)}$$

If the water discharge system is organized according to the new scheme (Figure 2), it would be possible to pump out the water collected in the mine using only 6 pumps.

Total power in this:

$$\sum N = N_1 + N_2 + N_3 + \dots = 4 \cdot 630 + 800 + 75 = 3395 \text{ kVt}$$

Overall productivity:

$$\sum Q = Q_1 + Q_2 + Q_3 + \dots = 4 \cdot 1250 + 850 + 320 = 6170 \text{ (m}^3\text{/hour)}.$$

Figure 3. Histogram of water discharge and electricity consumption of water collectors at the Angren mine.

CONCLUSION. It can be seen that if the operation of water extraction devices is organized according to the new scheme shown in Figure 2, only 6 pumps will be needed instead of 9 to pump water collected from the mine, resulting in a power saving of about 1000 kW and a productivity increase of 1900 m³/h. The histogram of the relationship between water volume and electricity is presented in Figure 3.

References:

1. Baymirzayev, B.J.. Mining stationary machine: textbook / B. J. Baymirzayev; UzR. - Tashkent: Science and Technology, **2019.** - 400 p.
2. Sodiqov A., Baratov B., «Mining stationary machines» study guide on the science. Tashkent, "NAVRuZ" publisher, **2015.**
3. A.P. Grchiko. V.I. Shcheloganov, Stationary machines and installations: textbook for universities. publishing house NUST MISIS. **2004**, 345 p.
4. A.P. Grchiko. Stationary machines Part 2 Mine dewatering, fan and pneumatic installations. publishing house Moscow **2007**, 24 p.
5. Dolganov A.V. Stationary machines: textbook / A.V. Dolganov. – M.: Publishing House of the Academy of Natural Sciences, **2017.** – 281 p.
6. Sodiqov A., Boymirzaev B., «Mining mechanics » guide to completing a course project in science. Tashkent, TSTU **2004**, 345 p.
7. Drozdova, L.G. Stationary machines: study guide. – Vladivostok: publishing house FESTU, **2007.** – 157 p.
8. N. V. Kalinkevich and I. A. Melnik Turbomachines. Fundamentals of the theory. Sumy State University **2017**, 78 p.
9. Popov V.M. Mine drainage installation M, Nedra, **1983.** 421 p.
10. V.N. Khadzhikov, S.A. Butakov Mining mechanics «Nedra», **1982.**
11. Abramov A.P., Bizenkov V.N., Stationary machines Calculation of dewatering plants for mining: study guide; - Kemerovo, **2003.**- 143 p.
12. Stationary machines and installations: textbook V.S.Soloviev, A.S.Smorodin; St. Petersburg State Mining Institute (Technical University). **2002.** 141 p.
13. Kartavy N.G., Toporkov A.A. Mine stationary installations: Reference manual. -M., "Nedra", **1978**, 263 p.
14. Burr N.G. Stationary machines: Sitebook for universities. -M., Nedra, 1981. 327 p.
15. Stationary installations of mines. Under the general editorship. B.F. Bratchenko. M., "Nedra", **1977**, 440 p.
16. High-Pressure Pumps Michael T. Gracey, P.E. Weatherford International Houston, TX Copyright **2006**, 245 p.